

Veneers – The Smile Healer

Yesh Sharma

Assistant Professor
Dept. of Conservative Dentistry
& Endodontics
Pacific Dental College & Hospital
Udaipur

Direct Composite Veneers Have Always Been A Challenging Technique For Dentists. While Composite Materials Continued To Develop And Improve The Method And Of Direct Composite Veneer Application Remained Unchanged¹. During The Years New Templates And Matrix Systems Have Developed But None Of Them Could Bring A Complete Solution To The Fact That The End Results Were Entirely Dependent On Dentist Skills. Dr. Itaymishael off Has Managed To Take All The Products Known In The Market And Combine Them Into One Complete System To Achieve Predictable Results Each Time And Without Being Time Consuming. In Order To Do So The Sectional Matrices Were Replaced By Full Anatomic One And Flowable Composite Material Was Used. The Ivener Matrix System Was Born.

Ivener Is The Only Injectable Composite Matrix System In The World. As A True Template, It Helps Dentists Create Beautiful, Long-lasting Direct Composite Veneers With Predictable Shape And Symmetry Every Time For Every Patient.

While There Are Many Types Of Composite Matrices On The Market, They Only Provide A Partial Solution, Requiring The Dentist To Shape Each Individual Veneer By Hand – A Time-consuming Process².

Use Cases- Multiple Diastemas, Stained Or Darkened Teeth, Peg Laterals, Chipped Teeth, Malpositioned Not Requiring Orthodontic

With Ivener, Clinicians Can Create A True, Natural-looking Template Used To Inject A Flowable Composite Material To Produce Durable And Easy-to-replicate Results In Minutes. Cut Down On Patient Chair Time, While Improving Results And Increasing Your Practice's Revenue³.

Any Curing Light Can Be Used With Ivener Templates. Ivener Matrices Are Compatible With Any Desired Flowable Composite Material

Unlike Prefabricated Veneer Systems You Can Use Your Own Composite Material And Do Not Have To Be Restricted By Thickness, Size, Cost And Shade⁴.

What Are The Advantages of The Ivener Upon The Other Products?

- No Or Minimal Tooth Preparation
- The Only System That Uses An Injectable Composite Without Having To Rely On Lab Work
- A True Natural Looking Teeth With Different Shapes And Sizes
- Results Do Not Rely Upon Dentist Skills
- Solves The Needs For Shape, Isolation, Gum Contour And A Proximal Area In One Single Injection
- Very Fast. Minutes Vs Conventional Layering Techniques That Takes Even Hours
- Reduces Chair Time
- Highly Profitable – Increases Acceptance Rate, The Capacity To Do More Dentistry, The Number of New Patients
- Can Be Used For Many Different Procedures Because It's A True Template
- Stress Reduction For Dentist And Staff

How Do Ivener Matrices Works?

After Etching And Bonding, The Translucent Matrix Is Applied Over The Tooth. Utilizing High Pressure, A Flowable, Composite Material Is Injected Through The Nozzle Of The Matrix, Filling It Complete. Once The Material Has Cured, The Templates Are Removed Revealing The Perfectly Contoured And Shining Surface⁵.

Dentists Who Use Ivener Templates Report That They Are Performing Many More Composite Veneer Procedures Than Before Because They Find The Process So Quick And Easy And Affordable For Their Patient's Which Has Led To Higher Case Acceptance.

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Step 1

Initial Situation

Step 2

Minimal tooth preparation and decay removal (if needed)

Step 3

Apply acid etchant to the tooth for 15-60 seconds.

Step 4

Rinse with copious amounts of water

Step 5

Apply Bonding Agent. Gently blow off excess with an air syringe leaving a thin layer of material.

Step 6

Light cure according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

Phase 2 : IVENEER

Step 7

Choose the right size and shape of the IVENEER matrix from the box.

Step 8

Apply the IVENEER matrix on to the teeth to be treated.

Step 9

Apply and connect the tip of the injectable composite syringe into the IVENEER matrix nozzle and inject until the whole template is filled with composite. Make sure it's free of air bubbles.

Step 10

Release the tip of the syringe from the nozzle

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